

INTELLECTUAL AND IMMATERIAL BANK

BY WISE JESTER

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TESTING IIB: a simple use case

TRANSFORMATION
COMPUTATION
SYMMETRY
ENTROPY
HUMOR

About IIB. Why humor?

Humor is a special area of cognitive science. Humor is about **clashing situations** that relate. The brain solves that and rewards itself with a smile or laugh, which cannot be faked. Humor is based on decomposition, which let people **play with** the elements and relations in a joke, in a way they can and prefer. That is key for collaboration, which always is a process, and processes tend to **transform**, often in a balance between certainty and uncertainty, specialized and hybrid knowledge, individual and collective **preferences**.

The Intellectual and Immaterial Bank (IIB) is a machine, which can show you how you think in a situation/process of uncertainty. You can find individuals and have a choice among several of them – just as they have towards groups of collaborating individuals. Both sides – independent professionals and collaborations in IIB – are beneficial to each other: they cover the needs in thinking change by relevant capacities and bring in complementary knowledge in a way that both sides learn something new. IIB is blind and it shows who you are as a set of capacities in thinking change, if you are an independent professional; and a set of collective needs in thinking change, if you are an author of a collaboration. To do that, IIB does not need to know your name, face, age, gender, social status, cultural and ethnic background, and things like that. IIB runs on humor. IIB is designed to deliver such results that are mutually beneficial in a mid and long run but are somewhat disrupting (read: “disturbing”) in a short run. IIB delivers change agents. Everybody can become a change agent for any group of people.

Team Wise Jester

What IIB is

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Problem: you have a CEO that talks bold speeches about innovation, but she pushes away ideas and avoids conversations about technology. You do not know how much time and effort it would take to change your CEO and/or re-organize the people environment around her, and you really would not like to make a fuss out of it...

Solution: you start with asking the CEO to "Begin as an author of a collaboration". Highly likely, the CEO would resist, because she "knows best", but you are stronger....

In blindness to facial data, individual professionals and collaborations (INSTRUCTION) may enjoy humor and see how they normally think in situations of experiment and fracture between the old and the new, find each other directly, and move on to their goals. Read [Terms of Use and Privacy](#).

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

The CEO re-discovers her own, original inner nature when she sees peaceful, neutral jokes, which are in need her own personal, subjective opinion as in nothing else in this world

One man was cleaning his ear with a cotton swab but pressed too hard and reset himself to the factory settings.

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In blindness to facial data, individual professionals and collaborations (INSTRUCTION) may enjoy humor and see how they normally think in situations of experiment and fracture between the old and the new, find each other directly, and move on to their goals. Read [Terms of Use and Privacy](#).

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

What are the domains of your professional interests formal and informal? Choose 5.
You can select what have you studied, worked with and are curios of, and what you simply love.

Physics

Engineering

Statistics

Math

XR

Robotics

Coding

Regulation

Economics

Gaming

Entrepreneurship

User experience

Social work

Writing

Music

Arts

Complex systems

Hybrid innovation

Communication

DONE!

The CEO is overwhelmed: finally, someone asked her what she likes

Moreover, creative spheres are listed along with "Regulation", so it does not look like crime, failure or foolishness to love Arts, Music or Writing. IIB is blind, so it won't disclose the CEO's name if she chooses at least one creative sphere along with the trendy, conventionally accepted, "serious" ones

The CEO is also provided with an opportunity to express what sort of knowledge her *de facto* group operates with, and that is not carved in stone either

The CEO receives her results, compiled with the results of her *de facto* group – and their issues with change thinking become evident!

Needs of my collaboration

- Your collaboration may have a challenge with fear of difference and novelty.
- Your collaboration may experience being too down-to-earth.
- Your collaboration might be overlooking the socially accepted.
- Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by pressuring the members.

In IIB, the CEO sees a set of change agents, either internally or from the outside, who would be uniquely understanding and not too bored if will be involved...

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis**. To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **collectivistic environments**. When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **imagination**. The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **regulation, communication, hybrid innovation**. The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, engineering**.

The people have not only their unique and relevant intellectual and immaterial capital as the necessary change agents...

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **breaking the old things down faster**. To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **high-pressure contexts**. When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **solidarity with the others**. The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **hybrid innovation**. The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, entrepreneurship, physics, music**.

...they may also bring in new knowledge, which may trigger a sudden novelty in the collaboration!

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis**. To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **independent genre**. When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **solidarity with the others**. The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **hybrid innovation**. The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **engineering, complex systems, economics, social work**.

...so, the intellectual change transition will be smoother

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

On the other side of the screen, any professional may find the collaboration, created by the CEO, and, while the CEO is still unsure – to be or not to be – she may be contacted by one or several independent professionals anyway

This is you

Your strongest capacity for making change is **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
You tend to react immediately to **cognitive signals.**
You prefer working in **collectivistic environments.**

A professional sees a set of collaborations, which could use the unique change thinking and the knowledge horizon of this professional

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **degree of inner passion of the members.**
What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **pressuring the members.**
This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **engineering.**
The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **physics, regulation, economics, entrepreneurship.**

IIB intensifies the smell of the actual self-realization of the persons' unique and specifically relevant intellectual and immaterial capital...

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **fear of difference and novelty.**
What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **pressuring the members.**
This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **math, xr, statistics.**
The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **entrepreneurship, complex systems.**

...in a knowledge environment, both compatible and new to them – that may trigger a sudden innovation in case of connection!

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **degree of inner passion of the members.**
What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **pressuring the members.**
This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **math, user experience.**
The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **hybrid innovation, complex systems, entrepreneurship.**

The CEO realizes the value of open mind, cognitive diversity, ability to take risks, and learns the skill of collaboration

In the meantime, the “misfits”, neutralized by the CEO, can now find comrades – from the previous endeavors or among completely new people – and begin their own collaborations

This is you

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **social signals.**
 You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**

...and the “misfit” may change the decision from leaving to staying, because previously it was impossible to prove to the CEO that the “misfit” can propose idiotic ideas, which may be right soon, considering that the CEO is now being organically disrupted too

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, gaming, statistics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics.**

...and the “misfits” new collaborations can result in novel, unconventional to their environment projects

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **imagination.**
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, statistics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics, robotics.**

with organic growth of the intellectual and immaterial capital, with hybrid knowledge, adaptive to the speed of progress

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **cognitive signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **breaking the old things down faster.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **math, engineering.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **complex systems, robotics, coding.**

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

...and in peace...

...collaborations and professionals – across entities, borders, silos... time frames – are being visible to each other in IIB

when the intellect and knowledge get attracted, from *ex situ* or *in situ*, towards a shared vision

Needs of my collaboration

- Your collaboration may have a challenge with **structures and processes that are stuck.**
- Your collaboration may experience **being too dispersed.**
- Your collaboration might be overlooking the **socially accepted.**
- Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by **pressuring the members.**

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **faster taking the new into practice.**
To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **collectivistic environments.**
When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **solidarity with the others.**
The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **coding, robotics.**
The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **statistics, physics, engineering.**

where spontaneity is directed towards overcoming mutual challenges, and towards the nature of meaningful performance

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **high-pressure contexts.**
When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **imagination.**
The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **xr, robotics.**
The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, entrepreneurship, engineering.**

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

where the competence is hybrid, not prestigious, and the minds are open and proactive

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **breaking the old things down faster.**
To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **contexts with high uncertainty.**
When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **focused aim.**
The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **coding, robotics.**
The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, math, engineering.**

and no one knows anyone before they get to see each other, and the fracture of their understanding of “normal” towards healthy change thinking begins with blindness...

...and so, the free movement of
intellect and knowledge, where
every node is empowered, favors
discovery, transformation and
emergent innovation

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You are very welcome!

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Genially,
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